

An expedient synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of ethoxyphthalimido derivatives of pyrimido[4,5-*e*]pyrimidine analogues from 1-(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-yl)guanidine

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Abstract : In the present study, convenient methods for the synthesis of new ethoxyphthalimidobenzimidazoles are elaborated. A novel pyrimido[4,5-*e*]pyrimidin-dione (5) and a series of pyrimido[4,5-*e*]pyrimidin-diones (8a-e) have been designed and synthesized starting from 1-(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-yl)guanidine (2). The structures of all newly constructed derivatives were corroborated by analytical and spectral data (FT-IR, ¹H NMR and Mass) and chemical tests. Subsequently, compounds were subjected to their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against a panel of pathogenic strains of bacteria and fungi. Some of the compounds were found to be equipotent or more potent than the reference drugs.

Keywords : Antimicrobial activity, guanidinobenzimidazole, pyrimidopyrimidine, ethoxyphthalimide.

Introduction

Pyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine of guanidinobenzimidazole system represents an attractive targets owing to their diverse pharmacological applications such as antiplatelet¹, tyrosine kinase inhibitor², antihistaminic, antiasthmatic³, antifolate⁴, antibacterial⁵, anti-inflammatory⁶, hepatoprotective⁷, antiviral⁸ etc. Many aminoxy compounds have been studied for their ability to inhibit the growth of the malaria parasite *Plasmodium falciparum in vitro*⁹. Heterocyclic rings attached to alkoxyphthalimide functionality have been synthesized and evaluated for cardiovascular¹⁰, antimicrobial^{11,12}, anti-malarial¹³ and anti-inflammatory¹⁴ activities.

From all the above findings and in continuation of our interest in the synthesis of novel alkoxyphthalimide-linked

heterocyclic framework from modified guanidine, our plan was to design and synthesize a new class of heterocyclic molecules in which all of the above moieties are present with the hope to achieve enhanced biological activities.

Results and discussion

Bromoethoxyphthalimide (1) was prepared by reported method¹⁵. The starting material 1-(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-yl)guanidine (2) was synthesized by the cyclocondensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with cyanoguanidine in the presence of 10% H₂SO₄. 4-Amino-2-(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-yl)aminopyrimidine-5-carbonitrile (3) was achieved by multi-component reaction between 2, triethyl orthoformate and malononitrile (Scheme 1). The structure of this compound was confirmed by IR (3464, 3343 cm⁻¹ : NH₂;

Scheme 1. Synthesis of pyrimidine analog of guanidinobenzimidazole.

Reagents and conditions : (1) 10% H₂SO₄, NaOH, reflux 1 h; (ii) CH(OEt)₃, CH₂(CN)₂, piperidine, stirr. reflux 45 min.

2154 cm^{-1} : $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and ^1H NMR (δ 11.98, 1H, br, s, NH), 8.52 (1H, s, =CH of pyrimidine) data. In first pathway, when 4-amino-2-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)aminopyrimidine-5-carbonitrile (**3**) was allowed to react with excess formic acid using trace of H_2SO_4 , it furnished 7-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)aminopyrimido[4,5-*e*]pyrimidin-4(3H)-one (**4**). The structure received support from IR (1695 cm^{-1} ; $\text{C}=\text{O}$) and ^1H NMR (δ 9.62, CONH) spectra. When **4** was treated with two equivalents of bromoethoxyphthalimide (**1**) in ethanol using pyridine as base, the resulting product was identified as the bis (phthalimidoxy) compound **5**. Its structure was supported by characteristic IR (1374 cm^{-1} ; N-O) and ^1H NMR (δ 3.55, 3.89, 2H, t each; for N- CH_2 and O- CH_2 of ethoxyphthalimide moiety) spectra. In another pathway, when **3** was treated with HCONH_2 , it gave N^2 -(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)pyrimido[4,5-

e]pyrimidine-2,5-diamine (**6**). It was further converted into the corresponding Schiff bases (**7a-e**) by reaction with various araldehydes. The presence of a new singlet at δ 8.4 for $-\text{N}=\text{CH}$ and a new strong band at 1572 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group confirmed the formation of the aldimine **7a**. Subsequently, on condensation with bromoethoxyphthalimide (**1**), **7a-e** furnished the bromoethoxyphthalimido derivatives **8a-e**. The structure of **8a** was confirmed by the appearance of two IR bands at 1246, 1368 cm^{-1} for $\text{CH}_2\text{-N-CO}$ and N-O groups and two new triplets at δ 3.44, 3.89 for N- CH_2 and O- CH_2 groups, respectively of ethoxyphthalimide moiety in its ^1H NMR spectrum. The synthesized compounds have also been characterized by their mass spectral and elemental analysis studies. Additional confirmation of ethoxyphthalimide group attachment was done by usual fluorescence test. All these reactions have been shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of ethoxyphthalimide linked derivatives **5** and **8a-e**.

Reagents and conditions : (i) HCOOH , H_2SO_4 , reflux 2 h; (ii) $\text{R}'\text{Br}$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, reflux 17 h; (iii) HCONH_2 , $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$, reflux 5 h; (iv) PhCHO , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, GAA , reflux 7–10 h; (v) $\text{R}'\text{Br}$, DMF , $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, reflux 14–20 h.

Experimental

Material and methods : Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel-G plates, *n*-hexane-ethyl acetate as developing solvent and the spots were exposed to UV light. FT-IR spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer BX spectrum on KBr pellets and NMR were recorded on a Bruker DRX-400 MHz spectrometer with DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts (δ) are referred in terms of ppm. Abbreviations for multiplicity are as follows : s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), and m (multiplet). The mass spectra were recorded on a Joel SX-102 (EI) mass spectrometer. Elemental analyses were done on "Heraeus Rapid Analyser". Structures of the synthesized compounds were characterized by IR, NMR, Mass and elemental analyses.

Synthesis of 1-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)guanidine (2) : *Ortho*-phenylenediamine (0.05 mol) were dissolved by heating in 50 mL of 10% sulfuric acid, and dicyandiamide (0.075 mol) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h and then 10 mL of 50% NaOH solution was added and heated for further 15 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and the resulting solid was collected by filtration, washed with cold water and dried. If compound was sufficiently pure, it was used without further purification. Yield : 86%, bright yellow solid, m.p. 238–240 °C. IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3456, 3247, 3198 (NH, NH₂), 3065 (Ar-H), 1606 (C=N), 1445 (C=C, Aromatic); ¹H NMR : δ 3.40 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.92 (1H, s, NH), 7.01–7.19 (4H, m, ArH), 11.14 (2H, br s, exchangeable, 2 × NH); GCMS *m/z* 175 [M⁺], 158, 133, 133, 116, 105, 88, 78, 63, 44, 41.

4-Amino-2-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)aminopyrimidine-5-carbonitrile (3) : A solution of compound 2 (0.01 mol) and an equimolar ratio of malononitrile in triethyl orthoformate (20 mL) in the presence of few drops of piperidine were heated with stirring under reflux for 45 min. The excess solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure, and the residue was cooled to rt. The precipitated solid was collected by filtration, washed with ethanol, dried and recrystallized from DMF. Yield : 74%, orange solid, m.p. >300 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₉N₇ : C, 57.37; H, 3.61; N, 39.02; Found : C, 57.48;

H, 3.79; N, 38.92%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3464, 3343, 3186 (NH, NH₂), 3026 (Ar-H), 2154 (CN), 1618 (C=N), 1454 (C=C, Aromatic), 1190 (C-N); ¹H NMR : δ 3.39 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.12–7.50 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.52 (1H, s, CH), 11.98 (2H, br s, exchangeable, 2 × NH); GCMS *m/z* 251 [M⁺], 226, 209, 185, 175, 158, 133, 119, 105, 90, 78, 63, 41.

7-(1H-Benzimidazol-2-yl)aminopyrimido[4,5-*e*]pyrimidin-4(3H)-one (4) : Compound 3 (0.01 mol) was added portionwise for 2 h to a mildly refluxing mixture of formic acid (25 mL) and sulfuric acid (1.5 mL). After an additional 30 min, the solution was cooled to 0–5 °C and poured onto crushed ice. The resulting precipitate was collected by filtration, washed with water, dried, and crystallized from ethanol to give 4. Yield : 68%, red solid, m.p. 296–298 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₉N₇O : C, 51.91; H, 3.25; N, 35.11; Found : C, 51.98; H, 3.19; N, 35.04%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3359, 3186 (N-H), 3035 (Ar-H), 1695 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1448 (C=C, Aromatic); ¹H NMR : δ 7.12–7.50 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.16 (1H, s, CH), 7.96 (1H, s, CH), 5.76 (1H, s, NH), 9.62 (1H, d, CONH); GCMS *m/z* 279 [M⁺], 252, 228, 209, 187, 175, 158, 144, 133, 118, 105, 90, 78, 57, 44.

Synthesis of compound 5 : Compound 4 (0.01 mol) and bromoethoxyphthalimide (1) (0.02 mol) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 mL). Pyridine (2 mL) was added to this solution, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 17 h in a round bottom flask. Excess of solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into crushed ice. Products were filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. Yield : 62%, light brown solid, m.p. 176–178 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₂₃N₉O₇ : C, 60.27; H, 3.53; N, 19.17; Found : C, 60.31; H, 3.45; N, 19.11%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3350 (N-H), 3035 (Ar-H), 1689 (CO-N-CO), 1615 (C=N), 1465 (C=C, Aromatic), 1374 (N-O), 1186 (C-N), 1048 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.16–7.74 (12H, m, Ar-H), 5.84 (s, NH), 8.12 (1H, s, CH), 7.95 (1H, s, CH), 3.89 (4H, t, OCH₂), 3.55 (4H, t, NCH₂); GCMS *m/z* 657 [M⁺], 468, 351, 334, 276, 251, 228, 209, 190, 187, 176, 158, 144, 146, 133, 105.

N²-(1H-Benzimidazol-2-yl)pyrimido[4,5-*e*]pyrimidine-2,5-diamine (6) : Compound 3 (0.01 mol) was dissolved in acetone and formamide (9.8 mL) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h. Resultant mixture

was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was poured on crushed ice and kept for 3 h at room temperature. Solid separated was filtered, dried and recrystallized from glacial acetic acid. Yield : 70%, bright orange solid, m.p. 274–276 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_9N_7$: C, 56.11; H, 3.62; N, 40.27; Found : C, 56.22; H, 3.67; N, 40.19%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3484, 3365, 3198 (NH₂), 3032 (Ar-H), 1605 (C=N), 1445 (C=C, Aromatic), 1179 (C-N); ¹H NMR : δ 3.45 (2H, s, NH₂), 8.09 (1H, s, CH), 7.84 (1H, s, CH), 5.69 (s, NH), 7.16–7.43 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.48 (1H, s, Ar-H); GCMS m/z 278 [M⁺], 262, 251, 224, 209, 183, 170, 158, 143, 132, 119, 105, 90, 77, 67, 42.

Synthesis of compound (7a) : Compound **6** (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of benzaldehyde (0.012 mol) in dry ethanol 40 mL in a round bottom flask, two drops of glacial acetic acid were added to the above mixture which was refluxed for 8 h. At the end of the reaction the solvents were partially evaporated then poured into water. The precipitates were collected by filtration, washed with ether, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. Compounds **7b-e** were also prepared by a similar method with minor changes in reaction conditions.

Compound 7a : Yield : 74%, creamish solid, m.p. 162–164 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{14}N_8$: C, 65.56; H, 3.85; N, 30.58; Found : C, 65.52; H, 3.77; N, 30.64%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3394, 3185 (N-H), 3022 (Ar-H), 1612 (C=N), 1428 (C=C, Aromatic), 1144 (C-N); ¹H NMR : δ 7.18–7.67 (9H, m, Ar-H), 8.44 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.11 (1H, s, CH), 7.96 (1H, s, CH), 5.92 (s, NH); GCMS m/z 366 [M⁺], 288, 279, 261, 252, 228, 209, 185, 175, 158, 144, 133, 118, 104.

Compound 7b : Yield : 76%, yellow-brown solid, m.p. 154–156 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{13}FN_8$: C, 62.50; H, 3.41; N, 29.15; Found : C, 62.46; H, 3.48; N, 29.11%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3352, 3158 (N-H), 3031 (Ar-H), 1624 (C=N), 1419 (C=C, Aromatic), 1149 (C-N); ¹H NMR : δ 7.19–7.64 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.42 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.14 (1H, s, CH), 7.99 (1H, s, CH), 5.84 (s, NH); GCMS m/z 384 [M⁺], 365, 289, 278, 262, 251, 223, 209, 183, 175, 158, 143, 133, 122, 118, 105.

Compound 7c : Yield : 71%, light brown solid, m.p. 146–148 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{13}ClN_8$: C, 59.93; H, 3.27; N, 27.96; Found : C, 59.87; H, 3.31; N, 27.89%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3381, 3174 (N-H), 3018 (Ar-H), 1635

(C=N), 1428 (C=C, Aromatic), 1150 (C-N); ¹H NMR : δ 7.17–7.68 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.48 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.19 (1H, s, CH), 8.01 (1H, s, CH), 5.67 (s, NH); GCMS m/z 402 [M⁺], 400 [M⁺], 364, 287, 279, 251, 226, 209, 185, 170, 158, 144, 139, 133, 118, 111, 105.

Compound 7d : Yield : 75%, white solid, m.p. 182–184 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{16}N_8O$: C, 63.62; H, 4.07; N, 28.27; Found : C, 63.67; H, 3.99; N, 28.31%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3392, 3196 (N-H), 3023 (Ar-H), 2872 (C-H str. CH₃), 1644 (C=N), 1418 (C=C, Aromatic), 1124 (C-N), 1045 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.16–7.70 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.45 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.11 (1H, s, CH), 7.85 (1H, s, CH), 5.72 (s, NH), 2.81 (3H, s, OCH₃); GCMS m/z 396 [M⁺], 366, 278, 251, 224, 209, 183, 170, 158, 144, 133, 118, 107, 90.

Compound 7e : Yield : 78%, cream-coloured solid, m.p. 159–161 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{19}N_9$: C, 64.53; H, 4.68; N, 30.79; Found : C, 64.45; H, 4.76; N, 30.85%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3312, 3196 (N-H), 3070 (Ar-H), 2892 (C-H str. CH₃), 1615 (C=N), 1435 (C=C, Aromatic), 1152 (C-N), 1040 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.11–7.65 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.49 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.16 (1H, s, CH), 7.89 (1H, s, CH), 6.09 (s, NH); GCMS m/z 409 [M⁺], 365, 279, 252, 223, 209, 183, 174, 158, 144, 135, 116.

Synthesis of compound 8a : A mixture of **7a** (0.01 mol) and **1** (0.01 mol) in DMF (25 mL) and pyridine (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 18 h in a round bottom flask. It was cooled to room temperature, and the mixture was slowly poured on to crushed ice with constant stirring. Solid obtained was filtered and washed twice with ice-cooled water. It was recrystallized from rectified spirit. Compounds (**8b-e**) were also synthesized by a similar method with minor changes in reaction conditions.

Compound 8a : Yield : 68%, brown solid, m.p. 132–134 °C, Anal. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{21}N_9O_3$: C, 64.86; H, 3.81; N, 22.69; Found : C, 64.82; H, 3.77; N, 22.64%; IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3382 (N-H), 3030 (Ar-H), 1695 (CO-N-CO), 1627 (C=N), 1421 (C=C, Aromatic), 1368 (N-O), 1246 (C-N), 1055 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.19–7.72 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.22 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.14 (1H, s, CH), 7.92 (1H, s, CH), 5.98 (s, NH), 3.89 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.44 (2H, t, NCH₂); GCMS m/z 556 [M⁺], 409, 379, 365, 289, 275, 251, 226, 209, 190, 185, 174, 162, 158, 143, 133.

Compound 8b : Yield : 66%, dark brown solid, m.p. 141–143 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₀FN₉O₃ : C, 62.82; H, 3.51; N, 21.98; Found : C, 62.88; H, 3.45; N, 22.04%; IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 3365 (N-H), 3028 (Ar-H), 1698 (CO-N-CO), 1624 (C=N), 1425 (C=C, Aromatic), 1372 (N-O), 1242 (C-N), 1051 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.20–7.78 (12H, m, Ar-H), 8.24 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.12 (1H, s, CH), 7.97 (1H, s, CH), 6.01 (s, NH), 3.96 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.40 (2H, t, NCH₂); GCMS *m/z* 573 [M⁺], 554, 428, 399, 383, 365, 289, 278, 262, 251, 223, 209, 183, 176, 158, 143, 133, 121.

Compound 8c : Yield : 63%, red-brown solid, m.p. 124–126 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₀ClN₉O₃ : C, 61.07; H, 3.42; N, 21.38; Found : C, 61.12; H, 3.47; N, 21.32%; IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 3349 (N-H), 3014 (Ar-H), 1694 (CO-N-CO), 1629 (C=N), 1431 (C=C, Aromatic), 1367 (N-O), 1230 C-N), 1048 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.19–7.74 (12H, m, Ar-H), 8.26 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.13 (1H, s, CH), 7.99 (1H, s, CH), 5.98 (s, NH), 3.85 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.48 (2H, t, NCH₂); GCMS *m/z* 592 [M⁺], 590 [M⁺], 553, 413, 445, 399, 364, 287, 279, 251, 226, 209, 192, 176, 158, 143, 139, 111.

Compound 8d : Yield : 65%, light brown solid, m.p. 149–152 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₃₁H₂₃N₉O₄ : C, 63.58; H, 3.96; N, 21.53; Found : C, 63.52; H, 3.89; N, 21.45%; IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 3352 (N-H), 3018 (Ar-H), 2865 (C-H str. CH₃), 1695 (CO-N-CO), 1631 (C=N), 1428 (C=C, Aromatic), 1370 (N-O), 1226 (C-N), 1052 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.21–7.79 (12H, m, Ar-H), 8.24 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.15 (1H, s, CH), 7.90 (1H, s, CH), 5.96 (s, NH), 3.92 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.54 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.85 (3H, s, OCH₃);

GCMS *m/z* 585 [M⁺], 554, 439, 423, 409, 395, 366, 251, 224, 209, 192, 183, 177, 158, 145, 131.

Compound 8e : Yield : 59%, pale brown solid, m.p. 177–179 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₆N₁₀O₃ : C, 64.21; H, 4.38; N, 23.40; Found : C, 64.16; H, 4.39; N, 23.48%; IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 3367 (N-H), 3056 (Ar-H), 2841 (C-H str. CH₃), 1698 (CO-N-CO), 1620 (C=N), 1412 (C=C, Aromatic), 1338 (N-O), 1202 (C-N), 1027 (C-O); ¹H NMR : δ 7.19–7.68 (12H, m, Ar-H), 8.20 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar), 8.08 (1H, s, CH), 7.84 (1H, s, CH), 6.16 (s, NH), 3.86 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.51 (2H, t, NCH₂); GCMS *m/z* 598 [M⁺], 555, 425, 410, 395, 367, 278, 252, 223, 191, 183, 176, 160, 146, 135.

Antimicrobial screening :

Compounds **5** and **8a-e** were studied for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against two Gram-positive bacteria, viz. *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and *S. pyogenes* MTCC 443 and two Gram-negative bacteria, viz. *Escherichia coli* MTCC 442 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* MTCC 441 by using ampicillin as the standard antibacterial drug. *In vitro* antifungal activity was also studied against three fungal species – *Candida albicans* MTCC 227, *Aspergillus niger* MTCC 282 and *Aspergillus clavatus* MTCC 1323 where Griseofulvin was used as the standard antifungal drug. The minimal inhibitory concentration (MICs, µg/mL) of the synthesized compounds was determined by the broth micro-dilution method according to National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards¹⁶. The results of this investigation are presented in Table 1. Compounds **8b** and **8c** exhibited strong antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* and also against *A. niger* and

Table 1. *In vitro* antimicrobial activity (MICs, µg/mL) of compounds **5** and **8a-e**

Compd.	Antimicrobial activity						
	Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity		
	Gram +ve		Gram -ve				
<i>S. aureus</i> MTCC 96	<i>S. pyogenes</i> MTCC 443	<i>E. coli</i> MTCC 442	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> MTCC 441	<i>C. albicans</i> MTCC 227	<i>A. niger</i> MTCC 282	<i>A. clavatus</i> MTCC 1323	
5	500	500	125	500	1000	200	125
8a	> 1000	250	200	1000	> 1000	250	200
8b	250	500	62.5	100	500	100	100
8c	500	1000	100	125	500	125	62.5
8d	500	200	250	250	1000	500	125
8e	1000	125	125	200	1000	200	250
Ampicillin	250	100	100	–	–	–	–
Griseofulvin	–	–	–	–	500	100	100

A. clavatus fungal strains and can be developed as potent chemotherapeutic agents. Our ongoing research focuses on the same molecular hybrids with incorporation of more effective substituents in search of new bioactive agents.

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